

Deep Learning-Driven Joint Beamforming and Channel Tracking via Sparse Bayesian Filtering for Massive MIMO

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Abstract—The temporal variation of massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) channels poses significant challenges to accurate channel estimation and effective beamforming design. To address this problem, we propose an end-to-end deep learning scheme for channel tracking with beamforming optimization. The proposed scheme integrates a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based beamformer fed by the sparse channel estimates to align with the dominant directions, together with an adaptive channel estimator using the online variational sparse Bayesian filtering (OVSBF) algorithm, which recursively updates the channel information at each time slot by leveraging temporal correlations. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposed approach achieves superior beam alignment and significantly outperforms other beamforming benchmarks.

Index Terms—Deep learning, massive MIMO, channel tracking, variational inference, Bayesian filter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) has become a key technology for modern wireless communication systems. Thanks to the large number of antennas, massive MIMO enables substantial spatial multiplexing capability and high angular resolution, thereby significantly improving spectral efficiency and sensing performance. In practical systems, however, fully digital architectures are often infeasible due to the high hardware cost. Therefore, hybrid analog–digital architectures are widely adopted [1], where only a limited number of radio frequency (RF) chains are available for digital processing. The analog beamformer restricts observations to low-dimensional projections of the high-dimensional channel.

This limited observability makes it challenging to acquire accurate channel state information (CSI). To address this issue, many existing works exploit the inherent sparsity of massive MIMO channels in the angular or delay domain, and develop various sparse channel estimation methods [2]–[5]. Specifically, [2] applies LASSO-based channel estimation and then designs the precoder using the Lanczos algorithm together with waterfilling. The work in [3] adopts a block sparse Bayesian learning (SBL) method and employs orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) to assist the hybrid beamforming design. More recent studies incorporate the deep neural network (DNN) into the joint optimization of channel

estimation and beamforming. In [4], a deep-unfolding network is proposed by unrolling the iterations of the approximate message passing (AMP) algorithm. In [5], the SBL procedure is similarly unfolded into multiple learnable layers. Both deep-unfolding approaches employ DNN-based beamforming, using the previous channel estimates as input.

Most of these approaches focus on static or quasi-static scenarios and do not fully account for the inherently time-varying nature of wireless channels caused by user mobility and environmental dynamics. As the channel evolves over time, both channel estimation and beamforming need to be performed in a tracking manner, further complicating the process. Moreover, existing studies on MIMO channel tracking [6]–[8] predominantly rely on iterative algorithms. Although these methods can exploit temporal channel correlation, they require multiple refinement iterations at each time slot. Therefore, these methods are not sufficiently adaptive for online tracking and can result in significant computational overhead in practical implementations.

Motivated by these issues, we propose an efficient channel tracking scheme as an extension of our prior work [9]. Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We propose an end-to-end deep learning framework that integrates a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based beamformer with an online channel estimator for tracking the time-varying massive MIMO channels.
- Inspired by [10]–[12], we propose an adaptive and non-iterative channel estimation algorithm, termed the online variational sparse Bayesian filter (OVSBF). The OVSBF performs recursive channel estimation based on the temporal evolution model while simultaneously inferring the unknown model parameters.

Notations: We use normal letters to denote scalars, lowercase bold letters for vectors, and uppercase bold letters for matrices, e.g., x , \mathbf{x} , and \mathbf{X} , respectively. The trace, conjugate, transpose, conjugate transpose, and inverse operators are denoted by $\text{tr}(\cdot)$, $(\cdot)^*$, $(\cdot)^T$, $(\cdot)^H$, and $(\cdot)^{-1}$, respectively. The expectation operator is denoted by $\langle \cdot \rangle$ or $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$, and the covariance operator by $\text{Cov}(\cdot)$. A set is denoted by $\{\cdot\}$, and \setminus^i denotes removing its i -th element. We denote the real part of a complex matrix \mathbf{X} by $\Re(\mathbf{X})$. We denote the Gamma

Fig. 1. Illustration of massive MIMO tracking systems.

distribution by $\text{Ga}(\cdot)$, the circularly symmetric Gaussian distribution and the real Gaussian distribution by $\mathcal{CN}(\cdot)$ and $\mathcal{N}(\cdot)$, respectively. We use $\|\cdot\|$ to denote the ℓ_2 -norm, $\|\cdot\|_F$ to denote the Frobenius norm, and \otimes to denote the Kronecker product. We use notation $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ for extracting the diagonal elements of a matrix or forming a diagonal matrix from a vector, $[\mathbf{x}]_i$ for the i -th entry of \mathbf{x} , $[\mathbf{X}]_{i,i}$ for the i -th diagonal entry of \mathbf{X} , $[\mathbf{X}]_{:,i}$ for the i -th column of \mathbf{X} , and $\mathbf{x}^{(1:t)}$ for the sequence from time step 1 to t .

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Model

Consider a narrowband massive MIMO system illustrated in Fig. 1, where the transmitter and receiver are equipped with N_t and N_r antennas, respectively, both arranged as uniform linear arrays (ULAs). The system employs $M_t (< N_t)$ and $M_r (< N_r)$ RF chains, with a fully-connected analog beamforming architecture. In the uplink closed-loop tracking scenario, the receiver tracks the time-varying channel and feeds its estimate back to the transmitter for the precoder design.

The time-varying MIMO channel $\mathbf{H}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_t}$ in the t -th time slot is modeled as

$$\mathbf{H}^{(t)} = \sqrt{\frac{N_t N_r}{N_c N_p}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \alpha_{i,j}^{(t)} \mathbf{a}_R(\theta_{i,j}^{(t)}) \mathbf{a}_T^H(\varphi_{i,j}^{(t)}), \quad (1)$$

where N_c and N_p are the numbers of clusters and paths per cluster, respectively, $\alpha_{i,j}^{(t)}$ is the complex fading coefficient, and $\mathbf{a}_T(\cdot) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{a}_R(\cdot) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times 1}$ are the transmit and receive steering vectors for ULA, with $(\varphi, \theta) \in [-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ denoting the angle of departure (AoD) and angle of arrival (AoA), respectively, given by

$$\mathbf{a}_T(\varphi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \left[1, e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin \varphi}, \dots, e^{j(N_t-1) \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin \varphi} \right]^T, \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_R(\theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_r}} \left[1, e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin \theta}, \dots, e^{j(N_r-1) \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin \theta} \right]^T, \quad (2b)$$

where λ is the wavelength, d is the antenna spacing. To capture the temporal dynamics of the channel, we adopt a first-order Gaussian Markov model, where the channel parameters $(\alpha_{i,j}^{(t)}, \phi_{i,j}^{(t)}, \theta_{i,j}^{(t)})$ evolve according to [8]:

$$\alpha_{i,j}^{(t)} = \rho \alpha_{i,j}^{(t-1)} + \Delta \alpha_{i,j}^{(t)}, \quad (3a)$$

$$\phi_{i,j}^{(t)} = \phi_{i,j}^{(t-1)} + \Delta \phi_{i,j}^{(t)}, \quad (3b)$$

$$\theta_{i,j}^{(t)} = \theta_{i,j}^{(t-1)} + \Delta \theta_{i,j}^{(t)}, \quad (3c)$$

where $\rho \in [0, 1]$ is the temporal correlation coefficient, and $\Delta \alpha_{i,j}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_\alpha^2)$, $\Delta \phi_{i,j}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\phi^2)$ and $\Delta \theta_{i,j}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\theta^2)$ are the Gaussian noise with their respective variances, respectively. To exploit the angular-domain sparsity of the channel, $\mathbf{H}^{(t)}$ can be represented in a sparse form $\mathbf{X}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{G_r \times G_t}$ as

$$\mathbf{H}^{(t)} \approx \mathbf{D}_R \mathbf{X}^{(t)} \mathbf{D}_T^H, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{D}_T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times G_t}$ and $\mathbf{D}_R \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times G_r}$ are the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) dictionaries constructed from the steering vectors, and G_t and G_r denote the number of angular grid points at the transmitter and receiver, respectively.

In the t -th slot, the combiner $\mathbf{W}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_r \times N_r}$ and the precoder $\mathbf{F}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_t \times N_t}$ are generated. Accordingly, the received signal $\mathbf{Y}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_r \times M_t}$ in the beam-space is expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y}^{(t)} = \mathbf{W}^{(t)} \left(\mathbf{H}^{(t)} [\mathbf{F}^{(t)}]^H \mathbf{S}^{(t)} + \mathbf{N}^{(t)} \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{N}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times M_t}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN), and $\mathbf{S}^{(t)}$ is the transmitted pilot matrix. For simplicity, let $\mathbf{S}^{(t)} = \mathbf{I}_{M_t}$, and we can express (5) in a vector form as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}^{(t)} &\approx \left[(\mathbf{F}^{(t)})^* \otimes \mathbf{W}^{(t)} \right] (\mathbf{D}_T^* \otimes \mathbf{D}_R) \mathbf{x}^{(t)} + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^{(t)} \\ &= \Phi^{(t)} \mathbf{x}^{(t)} + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^{(t)}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\Phi^{(t)} = ((\mathbf{F}^{(t)})^* \otimes \mathbf{W}^{(t)}) (\mathbf{D}_T^* \otimes \mathbf{D}_R) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times G}$ is the equivalent measurement matrix with $M = M_t M_r$ and $G = G_t G_r$, and $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{X}^{(t)}) \in \mathbb{C}^{G \times 1}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}^{(t)} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{W}^{(t)} \mathbf{N}^{(t)}) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ are the vectors of the sparse channel and noise, respectively.

B. Problem Formulation

We consider an online channel tracking problem, where the goal is to adaptively design the measurement matrix $\Phi^{(t)}$ to track the channel $\mathbf{H}^{(t)}$ (or equivalently $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$) from the received signal $\mathbf{y}^{(t)}$ in each time slot. Taking advantage of the temporal correlation of the channel, the measurement matrix for the current slot can be designed based on the prior channel information obtained in the previous slot [9]. Thus, the online channel tracking problem can be formulated as

$$\text{(P1)}: \min_{\mathcal{G}^{(t)}(\cdot), \mathcal{F}^{(t)}(\cdot)} \frac{\|\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{(t)} - \mathbf{H}^{(t)}\|_F^2}{\|\mathbf{H}^{(t)}\|_F^2} \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \Phi^{(t)} = \mathcal{G}^{(t)}(\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{(t-1)}), \quad (7b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{(t)} = \mathcal{F}^{(t)}(\mathbf{y}^{(t)} | \Phi^{(t)}), \quad (7c)$$

where $\mathcal{G}^{(t)}(\cdot)$ is used to generate $\Phi^{(t)}$ using the estimated channel $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{(t-1)}$ from the previous slot, and $\mathcal{F}^{(t)}(\cdot)$ is used to update the current channel estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{(t)}$. In (P1), the objective function is to minimize the normalized mean square error (NMSE) of tracking errors.¹

¹The NMSE serves as the loss function for training the deep learning scheme introduced in Sec III. In the online tracking stage, the optimized $\mathcal{G}^{(t)}(\cdot)$ and $\mathcal{F}^{(t)}(\cdot)$ are directly applied without knowing the true channel.

Fig. 2. The proposed scheme for MIMO channel tracking.

III. PROPOSED SCHEME

A. Description

We propose a deep learning scheme to address the online tracking problem in (P1), as illustrated in Fig. 2. The proposed scheme consists of two modules: the beamforming module, which implements $\mathcal{G}^{(t)}(\cdot)$ using a convolutional neural network (CNN), and the channel estimation module, which implements $\mathcal{F}^{(t)}(\cdot)$ using the online variational sparse Bayesian filtering (OVSBF) algorithm introduced in Sec. III-B. The beamforming module includes two CNN-based sub-networks that generate the precoder $\mathbf{F}^{(t)}$ and the combiner $\mathbf{W}^{(t)}$, respectively.² In this module, the input to these two sub-CNNs is the sparse matrix $\hat{\mathbf{X}}^{(t-1)}$, which is obtained by reshaping the previously estimated sparse vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1)}$ from the channel estimator. It is worth noting that $\mathbf{X}^{(t-1)}$, viewed as an image, exhibits clustered sparsity, and such structural characteristics can be effectively captured by CNNs [5]. Details of the CNN architecture and its parameter configuration are described in Sec. IV. In the following, we present the OVSBF algorithm used to obtain the sparse channel estimate.

B. OVSBF Algorithm

From (3), we note that when the AoD and AoA parameters vary slowly, the evolution of $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$ can be approximated by a linear model, given by

$$\mathbf{x}^{(t)} \approx \rho \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)} + \mathbf{z}^{(t)}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{z}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_{G \times 1}, \mathbf{\Gamma}^{-1})$ is the process noise with covariance $\mathbf{\Gamma} = \text{diag}([\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_G]^T)$. From (6), the measurement noise is assumed to follow $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_{M \times 1}, \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{I}_M)$ with precision β . The goal of the OVSBF algorithm is to track the sparse channel $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$ from the measurement $\mathbf{y}^{(t)}$ given by $\Phi^{(t)}$, while jointly inferring the parameters $\Theta = \{\mathbf{\Gamma}, \rho, \beta\}$.

1) *Bayesian Modeling*: We adopt a Bayesian inference framework incorporating recursive filtering to address this problem. To promote sparsity, we impose a hierarchical prior on $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$, modeling its entries as independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) zero-mean complex Gaussian variables:

$$p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{\Lambda}) = \prod_{i=1}^G \mathcal{CN}\left([\mathbf{x}^{(t)}]_i | 0, \frac{1}{\lambda_i}\right), \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{diag}([\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_G]^T)$. Under stationarity, it follows from (8) that $\mathbf{\Lambda} = (1 - \rho^2)\mathbf{\Gamma}$, or equivalently, $\lambda_i =$

²In this paper, only the beamforming part in $\Phi^{(t)}$ is optimized while the dictionary is fixed. The random beamforming is adopted as the precoder for comparison in the numerical results.

$(1 - \rho^2)\gamma_i, \forall i$. Thus, we can only infer $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ as an equivalent surrogate. To complete this hierarchical Bayesian model, we place Gamma hyperpriors on the precision parameters, i.e.,

$$p(\mathbf{\Gamma}) = \prod_{i=1}^G \text{Ga}(\gamma_i; a, b) = \prod_{i=1}^G \frac{b^a}{\Gamma(a)} \gamma_i^{a-1} \exp\{-b\gamma_i\}, \quad (10a)$$

$$p(\beta) = \text{Ga}(\beta; c, d) = \frac{d^c}{\Gamma(c)} \beta^{c-1} \exp\{-d\beta\}, \quad (10b)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ denotes the Gamma function. We note that large values of γ_i (or λ_i) drive the corresponding $[\mathbf{z}^{(t)}]_i$ (or $[\mathbf{x}^{(t)}]_i$) toward zero, thereby promoting sparsity. This mechanism is known as automatic relevance determination (ARD) [13]. Additionally, we assign a real Gaussian prior with mean μ_0 and variance σ_0^2 , to the temporal coefficient ρ :

$$p(\rho) = \mathcal{N}(\rho; \mu_0, \sigma_0^2). \quad (11)$$

Finally, the observation likelihood and the state-transition functions, derived from (6) and (8), can be written as

$$p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \beta) = \mathcal{CN}\left(\mathbf{y}^{(t)} | \Phi^{(t)} \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{I}_M\right), \quad (12a)$$

$$p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}, \mathbf{\Gamma}, \rho) = \prod_{i=1}^G \mathcal{CN}\left([\mathbf{x}^{(t)}]_i | \rho[\mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}]_i, \frac{1}{\gamma_i}\right). \quad (12b)$$

2) *Variational Inference*: To make the posterior inference tractable, we adopt variational Bayes with a mean-field factorization of the variational distribution $q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta)$ to approximate the posterior $p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t)})$, given by³

$$q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta) = q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})q(\Theta) = q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}) \prod_{i=1}^G q(\gamma_i)q(\beta)q(\rho), \quad (13)$$

where $q(\Theta) = \prod_{i=1}^G q(\gamma_i)q(\beta)q(\rho)$. Then, the evidence lower bound (ELBO) based on the marginal likelihood $\ln p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)} | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})$ is calculated by

$$\mathcal{L}(q) = \int q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta) \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})}{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta)} d\mathbf{x}^{(t)} d\Theta, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)}) &= p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta, \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \Theta, \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})p(\Theta | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)}) \\ &= \underbrace{p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \beta)}_{\text{Likelihood}} \underbrace{p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{\Gamma}, \rho, \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})}_{\text{Prediction}} \underbrace{p(\mathbf{\Gamma})p(\rho)p(\beta)}_{\text{Prior}}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and $p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{\Gamma}, \rho, \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})$ is a Gaussian predictive density conditioned on $(\mathbf{\Gamma}, \rho)$. Under the mean-field factorization, the

³We note that although $q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})$ can be fully factorized as $\prod_{i=1}^G q([\mathbf{x}^{(t)}]_i)$, as in [11], [12], enabling element-wise updates of $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$. However, these updates are inherently sequential and typically require multiple iterations, which limits parallelization and increases computational cost in practice.

variational distributions are updated by maximizing the ELBO as follows [14, Ch. 10]:

$$\ln q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}) = \mathbb{E}_{q(\Theta)} \left[\ln p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)}) \right] + \text{const}, \quad (16a)$$

$$\ln q(\Theta_i) = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})} \mathbb{E}_{q(\Theta_{\setminus i})} \left[\ln p(\mathbf{y}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \Theta | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)}) \right] + \text{const}, \quad (16b)$$

The following presents the derivation of each variational distribution in turn.

3) *Overall Computation:* The $\ln q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})$ is computed by collecting quadratic terms in $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$, yielding a Gaussian posterior distribution characterized by mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)}$ and covariance $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}$, given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} = \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} \left(\langle \beta \rangle [\Phi^{(t)}]^H \mathbf{y}^{(t)} + [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}]^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)} \right), \quad (17a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} = \left(\langle \beta \rangle [\Phi^{(t)}]^H \Phi^{(t)} + [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}]^{-1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (17b)$$

and the predictive distribution is approximated as Gaussian, i.e., $p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)}) \approx \mathcal{CN}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)}, \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)})$, given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)} &= \langle \rho \rangle \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}, & (18a) \\ \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)} &= \langle \rho^2 \rangle \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)} + \langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle (\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]^H) \\ &\quad + \langle \Gamma \rangle^{-1}, & (18b) \end{aligned}$$

where $(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}, \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)})$ corresponds to the previous variational estimate $q(\mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})$, and $\langle \rho^2 \rangle = \langle \rho \rangle^2 + \langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle$, with $\langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle$ denoting the variance estimate of ρ .

Proposition 1. *Eq. (17) yields the linear minimum mean square error (LMMSE) estimate in the information form, which is equivalently to the standard Kalman filtering update, i.e.,*

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)} + \mathbf{K}^{(t)} (\mathbf{y}^{(t)} - \Phi^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)}), \quad (19a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} = (\mathbf{I}_G - \mathbf{K}^{(t)} \Phi^{(t)}) \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}, \quad (19b)$$

with Kalman gain

$$\mathbf{K}^{(t)} = \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)} [\Phi^{(t)}]^H \left(\Phi^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)} [\Phi^{(t)}]^H + \frac{1}{\langle \beta \rangle} \mathbf{I}_M \right)^{-1}. \quad (20)$$

Proof: The result is obtained by applying the matrix inversion lemma to $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}$. ■

From (16b), we note that

$$\begin{aligned} \ln q(\Gamma) &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})} \mathbb{E}_{q(\rho)} [\ln p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \Gamma, \rho, \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})] + \ln p(\Gamma) + \text{const} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})} \mathbb{E}_{q(\rho)} [\ln p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}, \Gamma, \rho)] + \ln p(\Gamma) + \text{const}, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}, \Gamma, \rho)$ is given by (12b). Thus, the i -th variational distribution follows a Gamma distribution, that is,

$$\langle \gamma_i \rangle = \frac{a + 1}{b + [\mathbf{R}^{(t)}]_{i,i}}, \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{R}^{(t)} = \langle (\mathbf{x}^{(t)} - \rho \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}) (\mathbf{x}^{(t)} - \rho \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})^H \rangle$ shown in (23), and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t,t-1|t)} \triangleq \text{Cov}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})}(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})$ denotes the filtered cross-covariance matrix, which is computed based on the covariance update rule in (19b):

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t,t-1|t)} &= (\mathbf{I}_N - \mathbf{K}^{(t)} \Phi^{(t)}) \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t,t-1|t-1)} \\ &= \langle \rho \rangle (\mathbf{I}_N - \mathbf{K}^{(t)} \Phi^{(t)}) \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)}, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

with its previous estimate from time slot $t - 1$ defined as $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t,t-1|t-1)} \triangleq \text{Cov}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})}(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}) = \text{Cov}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})}(\rho \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}) = \langle \rho \rangle \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)}$. The term $\ln q(\rho)$ is calculated similarly by

$$\begin{aligned} \ln q(\rho) &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})} \mathbb{E}_{q(\Gamma)} [\ln p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \Gamma, \rho, \mathbf{y}^{(1:t-1)})] + \ln p(\rho) + \text{const} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})} \mathbb{E}_{q(\Gamma)} [\ln p(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} | \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}, \Gamma, \rho)] + \ln p(\rho) + \text{const} \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle} (\rho - \langle \rho \rangle)^2 + \text{const}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where the estimated variance and mean of ρ are given by (26). Finally, the expectation of β is given by

$$\langle \beta \rangle = \frac{c + M}{d + \left\langle \left\| \mathbf{y}^{(t)} - \Phi^{(t)} \mathbf{x}^{(t)} \right\|^2 \right\rangle}, \quad (27)$$

where $\left\langle \left\| \mathbf{y}^{(t)} - \Phi^{(t)} \mathbf{x}^{(t)} \right\|^2 \right\rangle = \left\| \mathbf{y}^{(t)} - \Phi^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} \right\|^2 + \text{tr} \left([\Phi^{(t)}]^H \Phi^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} \right)$.

4) *Algorithm Summary:* We first employ a diagonal approximation for the covariance matrices. Specifically, all covariance matrices in (18b), (19b), (24) could be updated via element-wise operations, given by

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}]_{i,i} &= \langle \rho^2 \rangle [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]_{i,i} + \\ &\quad \langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle \left[\left| \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)} \right|_i^2 + \frac{1}{\langle \gamma_i \rangle} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (28a)$$

$$[\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}]_{i,i} = \left(\langle \beta \rangle \left\| [\Phi^{(t)}]_{:,i} \right\|^2 + \frac{1}{[\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}]_{i,i}} \right)^{-1}, \quad (28b)$$

$$[\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t,t-1|t)}]_{i,i} = \frac{\langle \rho \rangle [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}]_{i,i} [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]_{i,i}}{[\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}]_{i,i}}. \quad (28c)$$

The computation in (22), (26) and (27) can be simplified by exploiting the diagonal structure. Thanks to this approximation, the per-step computational complexity is significantly reduced from $\mathcal{O}(G^2M + M^2G + M^3)$ to $\mathcal{O}(M^2G + M^3)$, with the Kalman gain update in (20) being the dominant cost. The OVSBF algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Proposition 2. *The OVSBF algorithm reduces to the standard sparse Bayesian learning (SBL) formulation [13], with the original version as a static special case.*

Proof: See Appendix A. ■

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{R}^{(t)} &= \left\langle \left(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} - \rho \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)} \right) \left(\mathbf{x}^{(t)} - \rho \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)} \right)^H \right\rangle_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})q(\rho)} \\
&= \left\langle \mathbf{x}^{(t)} [\mathbf{x}^{(t)}]^H \right\rangle_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})} + \langle \rho^2 \rangle \left\langle \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)} [\mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}]^H \right\rangle_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})} - 2 \langle \rho \rangle \Re \left(\left\langle \mathbf{x}^{(t)} [\mathbf{x}^{(t-1)}]^H \right\rangle_{q(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t-1)})} \right) \\
&= \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} + \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)}]^H + \langle \rho^2 \rangle \left(\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)} + \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]^H \right) - 2 \langle \rho \rangle \Re \left(\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t, t-1|t)} + \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]^H \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

$$\langle \rho \rangle = \langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle \left[2 \text{diag} (\langle \mathbf{\Gamma} \rangle)^T \text{diag} \left(\Re \left(\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t, t-1|t)} + \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]^H \right) \right) + \frac{\mu_0}{\sigma_0^2} \right], \tag{26a}$$

$$\langle \sigma_\rho^2 \rangle = \left[2 \text{diag} (\langle \mathbf{\Gamma} \rangle)^T \text{diag} \left(\Re \left(\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)} + \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}]^H \right) \right) + \frac{1}{\sigma_0^2} \right]^{-1}. \tag{26b}$$

Algorithm 1 Online Variational Sparse Bayesian Filtering (OVSBF) Algorithm

Input: Received signal $\mathbf{y}^{(t)}$, measurement matrix $\mathbf{\Phi}^{(t)}$, previous estimates $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t-1|t-1)}$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t-1|t-1)}$ and $\hat{\Theta}^{(t-1)} = \{\hat{\mathbf{\Gamma}}^{(t-1)}, \hat{\rho}^{(t-1)}, \hat{\beta}^{(t-1)}\}$.

Initialization: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(0|0)} = \mathbf{0}_{G \times 1}$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(0|0)} = \mathbf{I}_G$, $\hat{\mathbf{\Gamma}}^{(0)} = \mathbf{I}_G$, $\hat{\beta}^{(0)} = 1$, $\hat{\rho}^{(0)} = 1$, $(\hat{\sigma}_\rho^2)^{(0)} = 1$, $\mu_0 = 1$, $\sigma_0^2 = 10^2$, $a = 10^{-1}$, $b = 10^{-6}$, $c = 10^{-6}$, $d = 10^{-6}$.

- 1: **Prediction step:** Calculate the predictive mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)}$ by (18a) and covariance $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)}$ by (28a).
- 2: **Filtering step:** Calculate the filtered mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)}$ by (19a) and covariance $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}$ by (28b).
- 3: **Learning step:** Update parameters $\hat{\mathbf{\Gamma}}^{(t)}$, $\hat{\rho}^{(t)}$ and $\hat{\beta}^{(t)}$ by (22), (26) and (27), respectively.

Output: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)}$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}$, and $\hat{\Theta}^{(t)} = \{\hat{\mathbf{\Gamma}}^{(t)}, \hat{\rho}^{(t)}, \hat{\beta}^{(t)}\}$.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The system employs a $N_t = N_r = 32$ half-wavelength spaced MIMO array with $M_t = M_r = 16$ beams ($M = 256$). The channel dataset is generated based on (1) with $N_c = 3$ clusters and $N_p = 10$ paths, where the initial values are sampled from a Gaussian distribution for α and a uniform distribution for (θ, ϕ) . The channel then evolves following (3), with ρ set in the range $[0.9, 1)$, and the variances specified as $\sigma_\alpha^2 = 1 - \rho^2$, $\sigma_\phi^2 = 0.005$, and $\sigma_\theta^2 = 0.005$. We set the angular grid points to $G_t = G_r = 48$ ($G = 2304$). The SNR ranges from 0 to 20 dB, and is defined as $\text{SNR} \triangleq 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{H}^{(t)}\|_F^2}{\|\mathbf{N}^{(t)}\|_F^2} \right)$. For the two sub-networks, each CNN consists of a convolutional layer with a 5×5 kernel, an average pooling layer that maps the feature size from $G_r \times G_t$ to 16×16 , and two fully connected layers with widths $[256, 512, 2M_t N_t]$ (for precoder) and $[256, 512, 2M_r N_r]$ (for combiner). All layers employ the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function, and the final outputs are transformed into

complex-valued beamformers. We perform end-to-end training of the proposed scheme using the NMSE as the loss, with training epochs of 200, learning rate of 10^{-3} , and a batch size of 32. A total of 6000 channel realizations with 200 time blocks per realization are used for training, and 100 different channel samples for evaluation.

We first evaluate the proposed CNN-based beamformer, taking the combiner as an example. Fig. 3 shows the normalized energy, defined as the inner product between the combiner and the channel with respect to \mathbf{D}_R . The strong alignment with the dominant AoAs demonstrates the effectiveness of the CNN-based design in capturing the angular structure. We then compare the proposed CNN-based beamforming scheme with two benchmarks: random beamforming and singular value decomposition (SVD)-based beamforming, for both the precoder and the combiner. In the SVD case, the recovered channel $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^{(t)}$ is obtained from $\hat{\mathbf{X}}^{(t)}$ using (4), after which SVD is applied to extract the M_r and M_t dominant singular vectors for the combiner and precoder, respectively. Fig. 4 shows that the proposed OVSBF algorithm remains robust across different beamformers and significantly outperforms benchmark methods.

Finally, we evaluate the impact of the precoder and the size

Fig. 3. Normalized energy between the beamformer and the channel.

Fig. 4. NMSE of channel tracking versus SNR with different beamformers.

Fig. 5. NMSE of channel tracking versus N_t with different SNRs.

of the transmit antenna array. In this experiment, a random precoder and a CNN-based combiner are employed. The number of transmit antennas N_t is varied as [8, 12, 16, 24, 28, 32]. For each configuration, half of the transmit beams are used, i.e., $M_t = \frac{N_t}{2}$, the angular grid size is set to $G_t = \frac{3}{2}N_t$, and the other parameters remain the same. As shown in Fig. 5, the NMSE decreases monotonically as N_t increases, particularly at higher SNRs, indicating that a larger array with the optimized combiner can significantly improve channel tracking. At low SNRs, however, the performance tends to saturate, suggesting that tracking becomes noise-limited and that further improvements may require an optimized precoder to better exploit the transmit array gain.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a unified deep learning scheme for efficient channel tracking with beamforming design. In the online channel estimator, the proposed OVSFB algorithm is generalized as a dynamic version of the SBL by incorporating Bayesian filter, enabling recursive channel estimation while jointly inferring unknown model parameters. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed scheme. The future direction is to refine the approach to exploit structured sparsity more efficiently and to improve its robustness in cases where the angular parameters vary more rapidly.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

We remove all terms associated with ρ . In this case, the prediction in (18) becomes $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t-1)} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t-1)} = \langle \mathbf{\Gamma} \rangle^{-1} = \langle \mathbf{\Lambda} \rangle^{-1}$. Then, the posterior updates in (17) simplify to

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} = \langle \beta \rangle \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} [\mathbf{\Phi}^{(t)}]^H \mathbf{y}^{(t)}, \quad (29a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} = \left(\langle \beta \rangle [\mathbf{\Phi}^{(t)}]^H [\mathbf{\Phi}^{(t)}] + \langle \mathbf{\Gamma} \rangle \right)^{-1}. \quad (29b)$$

The mean of γ_i in (22) becomes

$$\langle \gamma_i \rangle = \frac{a + 1}{b + |\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)}|_i^2 + [\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)}]_{i,i}}, \quad (30)$$

where $\mathbf{R}^{(t)} = \langle \mathbf{x}^{(t)} [\mathbf{x}^{(t)}]^H \rangle = \hat{\mathbf{P}}^{(t|t)} + \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)} [\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t|t)}]^H$ is obtained by discarding the last two terms in (23). The update rule for β remains the same as in (27). Clearly, the above deviation recovers the standard SBL expression for complex-valued variables.

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